

Exploring Alfuzosin: Molecular Insights and Advanced Analytical Methods

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ABSTRACT

Alfuzosin, an alpha-adrenergic medication known by brand names such as Uroxatral, has garnered significant attention for its role in treating Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia (BPH). By blocking alpha-adrenergic receptors on the prostate, Alfuzosin alleviates BPH symptoms. This article provides an in-depth discussion of Alfuzosin's molecular structure, pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics, toxicity, indications, side effects, and drug interactions to better understand its mechanism of action and effectiveness. Various high-performance and spectroscopic techniques, including High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Reverse Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC), Reverse Phase-Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-UPLC), and ultraviolet spectroscopy, are used for identifying, quantifying, and elucidating the structure of Alfuzosin. The study presents an overview of Alfuzosin's characteristics and properties, along with the analytical methods used for its assessment and quantification.

Keywords: Alfuzosin, Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia, Alpha-adrenergic receptors, Analytical methods.

INTRODUCTION

Alfuzosin belongs to the α_1 blocker class of medications and is marketed under several brand names, including Uroxatral. It is used to treat (BPH). It acts as an antagonist of the α_1 -adrenergic receptor, relaxing the muscles in the bladder neck and prostate to facilitate urination. Alfuzosin was authorized for use in medicine in 1988 after being patented in 1978. In 2003, it received approval for benign prostatic hyperplasia in the United States. With almost 700,000 prescriptions, it ranked 336th among the most often prescribed drugs in the US in 2020[1]. BPH refers to the non-cancerous enlargement of the prostate, common in older men. Almost all men have BPH, or real hyperplasia of the prostate gland, which is a purely age-related condition that begins about age 40. Autopsy studies show the histologic prevalence of BPH is 10% in men in their 30s, 20% in their 40s, 50%-60% in their 60s, and 80%-90% in their 70s and 80s [2]. In the literature, BPH is defined in a number of ways. These consist of benign prostatic enlargement (BPE), LUTS, and bladder outlet

obstruction. Bladder outlet obstruction is described as a barrier to the flow of urine, BPH explains the histological alterations, and BPE refers to the enlarged size of the gland (typically subsequent to BPH). Benign prostatic obstruction is another name for BPE patients who have bladder outlet blockage [3]. BPH is a really hyperplastic process that causes the prostate's glandular-epithelial and stromal/muscle tissue to expand. This growth is frequently detectable and can take on many forms and configurations, which can affect symptoms and downstream consequences [4]. Beyond the hormonal effects of testosterone on prostate tissue, numerous other risk factors also contribute to the development of BPH. BPH does not occur in men who have an androgen-related disease or who are castrated prior to puberty. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) have been linked to BPH, although some studies have found a positive correlation while others have found no correlation at all. Because dihydrotestosterone (DHT) directly interacts with the prostatic epithelium and stroma to promote tissue growth and cellular proliferation, testicular androgens are necessary for

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the development of BPH [3]. Risk Factors for Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia (BPH) includes Age (Men older than 40 years old showed an increase in prostate volume of 2.0% to 2.5% year.), Heredity (According to some research, BPH is inherited in an autosomal dominant manner. Early development of clinical symptoms and greater prostatic volumes are common in men with a positive family history.) and Geography (being more in Western countries than in South-East Asian countries) [6]. The aforementioned risk variables—geography, age, and heredity—are referred to as non-modifiable risk factors, and they are important contributors to the development of BPH. Modifiable risk factors for BPH include metabolic syndrome, inflammation, sex hormones, cardiovascular disease, obesity, and lack of physical exercise [6].

2. Alfuzosin.

Alfuzosin, a new quinazoline derivative, selectively and competitively antagonizes α_1 -adrenoceptors, inhibiting the contraction of prostatic capsule, prostatic, proximal urethral smooth muscle, and bladder base, thus reducing the tone of these structures [7].

Figure 1: -Chemical structure of Alfuzosin

Source: Chemical structure of Alfuzosin, Chem3D Pro version 7.0.0 software [8]

2.1 Physiochemical properties

The compound IUPAC name is (RS)-N-[3-[(4-Amino-6,7-dimethoxy-quinazolin-2-yl)-methyl-amino]propyl] tetrahydrofuran-2-carboxamide [9]. Alfuzosin hydrochloride is a white to off-white crystalline powder with a melting point of around 240°C. It dissolves freely in water, is sparingly soluble in alcohol, and almost insoluble in dichloromethane. The compound has an average molecular weight of 389.4488 g/mol and a monoisotopic weight of 389.2063 g/mol. It is also referred to by the names Alfuzosina, Alfuzosine, and

Alfuzosinum. This solid has a boiling point of 688°C, a melting point of 240°C, and a solubility of 92 mg/L in water at 25°C. Its vapour pressure is 4.56×10^{-13} mm Hg at 25°C, with a Log P value of 1.604 [9].

2.2 Mechanism of Action

Alpha(1)-adrenoreceptors are located in the prostate, prostatic capsule, bladder neck, bladder base and prostatic urethra. Activation of these receptors can cause smooth muscle contraction, leading to urinary symptoms in patients with Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia (BPH). Alfuzosin specifically targets and inhibits alpha(1)-adrenergic receptors located in the lower urinary tract, helping to alleviate urinary symptoms associated with conditions such as Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia (BPH). This relaxation of smooth muscle in both the prostate and bladder neck improves urine flow and reduces urinary symptoms in patients [9].

2.3 Pharmacology

2.3.1 Pharmacokinetics

Absorption: Alfuzosin has a 49% absolute bioavailability when eaten and is easily absorbed in the gastrointestinal tract. Alfuzosin is absorbed more quickly and has greater peak plasma levels in persons over 75. According to one report, the bioavailability is 64%. Eight hours after several doses under fed settings, C_{max} is reached. AUC: 0-24 and C_{max} are approximately 194 ng/mL and 13 ng/mL, respectively. Following the second dose, steady-state plasma concentrations are attained, which are 1.2–1.6 times greater than those following a single dose. The extended-release formulation of Alfuzosin maintains its release for 20 hours, with a dissolution rate ranging from 2 to 12 hours [9].

Volume of distribution: Following intravenous administration, alfuzosin has a volume of distribution of approximately 3.2 L/kg in healthy volunteers. It distributes extensively to the prostate tissues, which is indicative of its targeted action in treating conditions such as Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia (BPH) [9].

Protein binding: Alfuzosin has a modest protein binding range of 82% to 90%. Alfuzosin has a 52.5%

binding to human serum alpha-glycoprotein and a 68.2% binding to human serum albumin [9].

Metabolism: 11% of the dose administered of Alfuzosin is found in the urine unaltered due to the drug's substantial hepatic metabolism. Three metabolic pathways- oxidation, N-dealkylation and O-demethylations - are involved in the metabolism of

Alfuzosin. Alfuzosin's metabolites lack pharmacological activity, and the primary hepatic cytochrome enzyme in charge of its metabolism is CYP3A4 [9].

Route of elimination: It is mostly eliminated in the bile and stool after being slightly metabolized. After a week of oral administration [9].

Table 1. Route of Elimination of Alfuzosin

Administration	Substance	Urine Radioactivity	Faeces Radioactivity
Oral	Radiolabeled Alfuzosin solution	24%	69%

Biological half-life: Alfuzosin has an apparent half-life of ten hours following oral ingestion. Three to five hours is the terminal half-life [9].

Clearance: If renal clearance is less than 30 mL/min, proceed with caution. Renal insufficiency (with or without dialysis) increases the clearance of Alfuzosin because the free fraction rises [9].

Toxicity: Alfuzosin's oral LD50 in male mice is 2300 mg/kg, while in female mice it is 1950 mg/kg. Hypotension may result from an Alfuzosin overdose. Cardiovascular assistance ought to be started very early. To help restore pressure and control heart rate, the patient should remain in the supine posture. In extreme situations, fluid resuscitation should also be considered; vasopressors may be necessary. Regular monitoring of renal function is necessary. Dialysis might not help with up to 90% of Alfuzosin protein binding [9].

2.3.2 Pharmacodynamics

Alfuzosin improves urine flow and lessens the symptoms of BPH by selectively blocking alpha adrenergic receptors in the lower urinary tract. This relaxes the smooth muscles in the prostate and bladder neck. Alfuzosin also causes peripheral vasodilation by lessening the vasoconstrictor impact of catecholamines, such as norepinephrine and adrenaline. Patients who take nitrates, antihypertensives, or have suffered a drop in blood pressure after taking other medications should be cautious, according to medical advice, as this

increases the risk of postural hypotension/syncope [9].

2.3.3 Uses, Side Effects, and Drug Interactions

Alfuzosin is used to treat symptoms of BPH in men, such as painful urination, frequent and urgent urination, and trouble urinating (weak stream, dribbling, hesitation, and incomplete bladder emptying). Common infection symptoms include headache, runny or stuffy nose, discomfort, nausea, constipation, heartburn, stomach pain, fever, chills, cough, and impaired sexual ability. Drug interactions include increased serum levels with abametapir, reduced metabolism with acalabrutinib, decreased therapeutic effectiveness with salbutamol, slowed metabolism with aldesleukin, and an increased risk of QTc prolongation with amantadine.

3. Analytical methods

Technological advancements have resulted in the creation of advanced analytical instruments, significantly improving the precision and sensitivity of analytical methods. Techniques such as HPLC, UPLC, High-Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPTLC), and Ultra-Violet (UV) analysis are now essential in modern analytical chemistry. Table 1 provides various analytical methods performed on Alfuzosin and various combinations of Alfuzosin.

Table 1. Analytical methods developed on Alfuzosin

S.N O	DRUG	METHODS USED	COLUMN DETAILS	MOBILE PHASE	DETECTION (nm)	INJECT ION VOLUME (ml/min)	FLOW RATE	STATISTICAL DATA ANALYSIS	RUN TIME	MATRICES	RETENTION TIME (min)	Comments	References
1	Alfuzosin and Dutasteride	RP-HPLC	Phenomenonex C18 column (250mm × 4.6mm, 5 µm particle size)	Methanol: water (80:20v/v)	UV (264nm) PDA detector	NA	1.0ml/min	Alfuzosin-LOD=0.07 µg/ml	NA	capsule	Alfuzosin = 4.18min Dutasteride = 2.94min	Selective, Precise, Accurate	[10]
2	Alfuzosin Hydrochloride and Dutasteride	RP-HPLC	XterraC18 (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer(pH 6.5): Water (75:15:10)	UV (245nm)	NA	0.8 mL/min	LOQ=0.21 µg/ml LOD = 0.0045 µg/ml for ALFU and 0.03 µg/ml for DUTA.	NA	Pharmaceutical dosage forms	Alfuzosin = 2.3min Dutasteride = 4.3min	Good Accuracy, Precision, Selectivity, And Robustness	[11]
3	Alfuzosin HCl Solifenacin Succinate	HPTLC	Silicone gel 60 F25 4	Ethyl Acetate: Toluene: Ethanol: Ammonia (5:2:3:0.4, By Volume)	220 nm and visualized by iodine vapor in daylight	NA	NA	r ² =0.9998	NA	Solital® capsules	NA	Good Linearity	[12]
4	Alfuzosin Hydrochloride	RP-UPLC	Waters Acquity HSS T3 C18, 100 mm × 2.1 mm, particle size 1.8	Acetonitrile, Tetrahydrofuran (99:1)	UV (254nm)	2.00 µL	0.3mL/min	Dutasteride – LOD=0.06 µg/ml	6.5 min	NA	6.0 min	Accurate, Precise, Specific	[14]
5	Alfuzosin Hydrochloride	UV – Spectrophotometric	NA	NA	350nm	NA	NA	LOQ=0.17 µg/ml r ² =0.994	-	Tablets	NA	Simple, Precise, Reliable, Accurate, Economical and Rapid Method	[15]
6	Alfuzosin enantiomers & Solifenacin	HPLC	Shorter column of 50mm length	Ethanol And Phosphate Buffer, Ph 4, (30:70, V/V)	215nm	NA	0.5mL/min	r ² =0.9999	3 min	Pharmaceutical combination	NA	Safer, More Economic, Eco-Friendly	[16]
7	Alfuzosin and Dutasteride	RP-HPLC	XTerra C18 Column (150×4.6mm, 5µm particle size)	Ammonium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 6.5) and methanol (25:75 proportions)	UV (246 nm)	20 µL	1.0 mL/min	R ² = 0.999 Alfuzosin LOD and LOQ 0.41 and 0.71 µg/mL Dutasteride = LOD and LOQ 4.27 and 2.14 µg/mL respectively	6 min	API and Pharmaceutical dosage form	Alfuzosin = 2.14min Dutasteride = 4.26min	Simple, Precise, Reliable, Accurate, Economical and Rapid Method	[17]

8	Alfuzosin hydrochloride	UV – Spectrophotometric	NA	0.1M NaOH	$\lambda_{\max} = 350$ nm.	NA	NA	$r^2 = 0.999914$	NA	Tablet	NA	Simple, Rapid, Sensitive and Accurate	[18]
9	Alfuzosin hydrochloride	UV-visible spectrophotometer	NA	Methanol	$\lambda_{\max} = 600$ nm.	NA	NA	NA	NA	Bulk and Pharmaceutical formulations	NA	Highly reproducible	[19]
10	Alfuzosin Hydrochloride	RP-HPLC	Inertsil ODS-3V (5 μ m, 15 cm x 0.46 cm)	Acetonitrile : Water : TetraHydroFuran : Perchloric acid (250:740:10:1)	245nm	10 μ l.	1ml/min	$r^2 = 0.999$ %RSD=0.71% Tailing Factor=1.07	NA	Tablet	NA	Simple and Reliable HPLC Method	[20]
11	Alfuzosin	HPLC	BDS Hypersil-C18 column (50 mm x 4.6 mm i.d., particle size 5 μ m) BDS Hypersil-C18 column(50mm x 4.6mm x 5 μ m)	25 % v/v acetonitrile and 75 % v/v water (containing 1ml/L triethylamine as peak modifier, pH adjusted to 2.5 \pm 0.1 with orthophosphoric acid 25 % v/v acetonitrile and 75 % v/v water (containing 1ml/L triethylamine as peak modifier, pH adjusted to 2.5 with orthophosphoric acid)	Atenolol - Excitation wavelength= 222 nm and emission wavelength= 300 nm Alfuzosin - Excitation wavelength= 265 nm and emission wavelength= 380 nm	NA	0.5ml/min	$r^2 = 0.999$	4min	Human Plasma	Atenolol=1.5min Alfuzosin=2.3min	The HPLC process is straightforward, extremely sensitive, quick, precise, and cost-effective.	[21]
12	Alfuzosin	RP-HPLC	C18 column(150 mm x 4.6 mm) Precoated TLC silica gel aluminum plates 60F254 (20 15 cm, 200 μ m thickness)	0.02 mol·L ⁻¹ phosphate buffer(pH 2.5)-acetonitrile(40:60)	Excitation wavelength= 374 nm and emission wavelength= 378 nm	NA	1.0ml/min	$r^2 = 0.999$ LOD=0.78 ng/mL	NA	Human Plasma	NA	Straightforward method	[22]
13	Alfuzosin, Terazosin, Prazosin, Doxazosin and Finasteride	HPTLC		Methylene chloride:N-Hexane:Methanol (8.8:0.3:0.9, by Volume)	Alf, Ter, Prz and Dox- 254 nm Fin-220nm	5 μ l.	0.15 μ l/s	$r^2 = 0.999$ LOD=7.85 ng/spot 9.78 ng/spot 4.62 ng/spot 9.56 ng/spot 60.58 ng/spot for Alf,	NA	Pharmaceutical dosage form	Rf= 0.26, 0.36, 0.45, 0.59 and 0.69 for ALF, TER, PRZ, DOX	High Sensitivity, Simplicity And Selectivity	[23]

								Ter, Prz, Dox & Fin respectively LOQ= 23.80 ng/spot 29.64 ng/spot 14.00 ng/spot 28.98 ng/spot 183.59 ng/spot respectively			and FIN, respectively.		
14	Sildenafil citrate (SIL) and Alfuzosin hydrochloride (ALF)	Green micellar RPLC	C18 column	0.005 M Brij-35 in water; pH 2.5 adjusted with 0.1% orthophosphoric acid	225 nm	NA	1 mL/min	Linearity= 0.5–40, 2.5–62.5 µg/mL for ALF and (SIL), respectively.	NA	Tablet Dosage form	NA	Green analytical chemistry	[24]
15	Sildenafil citrate (SIL) and Alfuzosin hydrochloride (ALF)	Classical RPLC	C18 column	Methanol, acetonitrile, and 0.02 M potassium dihydrogen phosphate (43:14:43 v/v; pH 4.66)	225nm	NA	1.3 mL/min	Linearity= 5–62.5 µg/mL	NA	Tablet Dosage form	NA	Rectilinear	[24]
16	Alfuzosin	LC-ESI-MS/MS	C18 column	Diethyl ether-Dichloroethane (70 : 30, v/v)	Turbo ion spray interface	NA	NA	Linearity=0.20–30 ng/mL	4.0 min	Human Plasma	NA	Precise, Accurate, Rapid, Selective and Sensitive	[25]
17	Alfuzosin, Tamsulosin and Vardenafil	HPLC	Phenyl-hexyl column (250 × 4.6 mm i.d.)	Acetonitrile/0.25% Phosphoric acid (30:70, v/v)	246/450 nm for Alfuzosin & Vardenafil, and 226/322 nm for Tamsulosin	NA	1.2 mL/min	LOD=0.56 ng/mL, 0.98 ng/mL and 2.81 ng/mL, alfuzosin, vardenafil and tamsulosin respectively	7.0min	Human plasma and pharmaceutical formulations	ALF, VAR and TAM were 3.35, 5.05, and 6.45min respectively	Sensitive and simple	[26]
18	Alfuzosin hydrochloride & Tadalafil	Green spectrophotometric Method	NA	Ethanol	λiso = 272nm	NA	NA	LOD=0.132 µg/mL & 0.530 µg/mL for alf & tad respectively LOQ=0.401 µg/mL & 1.606 µg/mL for alf & tad respectively Linearity=0.9999	NA	Tablet	NA	Accurate, precise and selective	[27]

An economical RP-UPLC technique has been developed for the analysis of alfuzosin hydrochloride, is accurate, exact, and specific even when contaminants and breakdown products from forced decomposition are present. The chromatographic process is more economical when less solvent is used. [13]. The article describes the RP-HPLC technique, which uses UV detection at 264 nm and is straightforward, specific, repeatable, exact, and robust, for measuring alfuzosin and dutasteride simultaneously in capsules. [10]. For the simultaneous measurement of dutasteride and alfuzosin in pharmaceutical dosage forms, a simple, economical, rapid, accurate, and precise reverse-phase high-pressure liquid chromatographic technique was created and approved. [11]. Alfuzosin hydrochloride in Solitral® capsules could be satisfactorily measured using the HPTLC technique, which has been developed and validated. This approach is perfect for everyday quality control and research since it has demonstrated exceptional accuracy, precision, selectivity, and resilience. [12]. The accuracy, precision, assay, robustness, ruggedness, limit of detection, and limit of quantitation of the study report on the UV technique for measuring alfuzosin were all verified [14]. Two enantiomers of ALF and SOL coupled in a novel dosage form were effectively determined simultaneously using a new chiral HPLC approach [16]. A straightforward, accurate, dependable, affordable, and quick approach was created for determining ALF and DUT from API and pharmaceutical dose forms [17]. The suggested UV spectroscopic approach is easy to use, quick, precise, cost-effective, and beneficial for routinely analyzing alfuzosin hydrochloride from commercial formulations [18]. The suggested UV spectroscopic approach is highly reproducible [19]. Alfuzosin hydrochloride in bulk pharmaceutical dose formulation can now be measured using an easy-to-use and trustworthy HPLC approach. Therefore, it can be suggested for this drug's regular quality control [20]. The development of a High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) method for quantifying alfuzosin in human plasma. This method is often designed to be sensitive, precise, and efficient, adhering to validation guidelines for pharmaceutical or clinical studies [21]. A robust RP-HPLC method was successfully developed and validated for the determination of alfuzosin in human plasma,

demonstrating high sensitivity, precision, and accuracy. The method meets analytical requirements for biological preparation with excellent recovery and linearity [22]. HPTLC requires significantly smaller quantities of solvents, making it both cost-effective and environmentally sustainable. Additionally, it is a rapid analytical technique capable of processing numerous samples simultaneously without any carryover effects [23]. The methods successfully quantified the binary mixture in tablet dosage form and assessed their stability, validated per ICH guidelines and system suitability. These methods were also evaluated using green analytical chemistry tools: National Environmental Methods Index, analytical Eco-Scale score, and Green Analytical Procedure Index [24]. A precise, accurate, quick, selective, and sensitive LC-ESI-MS/MS technique for quantifying alfuzosin in human plasma has been developed and validated, using amlodipine as the internal standard [25]. ALF, VAR, and TAM in dose forms and spiked human plasma samples are sensitive, easy, and well-suited for rapid determination with a 7-minute analysis time [26]. The techniques used to measure the amounts of tadalafil and alfuzosin hydrochloride in their mixed tablets were exact, accurate, and selective [27].

CONCLUSION

Alfuzosin appears as an alpha blocking medicine in the ongoing war against Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia. This review discusses with molecular structure, mechanism of action, pharmacology which encompasses pharmacodynamic, pharmacokinetics, toxicity, indications, side effects & drug interactions. This review also emphasizes the critical role that different analytical techniques play in comprehending the properties of alfuzosin and evaluating its potential for therapeutic use. Methods like UV Spectroscopy, HPLC, RP-HPLC, and RP-UPLC have been crucial in determining, measuring, and clarifying alfuzosin's structural characteristics, which has aided in its creation and clinical assessment.

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